

Resources on how to create a research software engineering (RSE) group (within an organisation) or association (national, etc)

Some of these resources are sourced from other documents including:

1. [ADORE software toolkit](#) by ReSA.
2. [CommuneRS: A Community of Research Software Communities](#) by Ella Kaye et al.
3. RSE Groups in the UK; Origins, Organisational Context, and Practices - '[RSE Roadtrip Planning Document](#)' by Kim Martin.
4. [RSE Resources](#) by US-RSE.

Starting an RSE group within an organisation (a university, national lab, company, etc)

1. [Anatomy of a Central RSE Team](#) by Matthew Bluteau, 2023.
2. [Getting Started with the RSE Movement within your Organisation: A Guide for Individuals](#) by Rinku Gupta et al., 2023.
3. [How do RSE groups work?](#) By Willi Usher et al., 2020.
4. [How to start an RSE Group](#) by Jeremy Cohen, 2019.
5. [How to start an RSE Group](#) by Society of RSE, 2019. Provides case studies from 14 research organisations in the UK and USA.
6. [The Princeton University Research Software Engineering Group Model: Operational and Organizational Approaches](#) (and [preprint](#)) by Ian A. Cosden.
7. [Program Pilot: Getting Started with the RSE Movement within your Organization](#) by the US-RSE RSE Empowerment in National Labs Working Group
8. [RSE-leaders/evidence-bank](#) from the RSE Group Evidence Bank. Contains case studies showing different roles within RSE groups in various institutions.
9. [Research Software Development & Management in Universities: Case Studies from Manchester's RSDS Group, Illinois' NCSA, and Notre Dame's CRC](#) by Daniel S. Katz et al., 2019.
10. [RSE Starter Pack](#). Includes definitions for RSEs, community website template, etc.
11. [RSEs in Research? RSEs in IT?: Finding a suitable home for RSEs](#) by Jeremy Cohen and Mark Woodbridge, 2020.

Starting an RSE association (regional, national, multinational associations and societies)

1. [Growth of the US-RSE Association](#) by Ian Cosden and Sandra Gesing, 2019.
2. [How to set up a national RSE association?](#) By James Hetherington et al., 2018.

Resources on building communities generally - useful for starting an RSE association

1. [Building a local community of practice in scientific programming for life scientists](#) by Sarah L. R Stevens et al. A model to build a CoP at a local academic institution,
2. [Community-development](#) from the Carpentries. Ideas and resources to support community building efforts by Carpentries community members as part of the Community Development Program

3. [Community Participation Model](#) by the Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE). Describes four modes of member engagement,
4. [Guide to Planning a Community](#) from The Turing Way.
5. [Seven Principles for Cultivating Communities of Practice](#) by Etienne Wenger-Trayner. A practical guide to making knowledge work inside an organisation.
6. [10 rules for building communities](#) by Christoph Junghans and Mark C. Miller. Rules for helping newcomers become contributors to open projects,
7. [Ten Simple Rules for Running a Successful Community of Practice](#). Rules proposed at a 2019 SSI event formalising the three components of communities of practice.

Resources related to RSEs more generally

1. [Bridging the gap: Structures for efficiently supporting research software roles and careers at academic institutions](#) by Jeremy Cohen, 2024.
2. [Ten reasons to be a research software engineer](#) by C. Cannam et al., 2013.
3. [Foundational Competencies and Responsibilities of a Research Software Engineer](#) (Goth et al., 2023) explores educational paths for Research Software Engineers.
4. [The Four Pillars of Research Software Engineering](#) by Jeremy Cohen et al., 2021.
5. [Hiring, Managing, and Retaining Data Scientists and Research Software Engineers in Academia: A Career Guidebook from ADSA and US-RSE](#).
6. [NITheCS Mini-school: Research Software Engineering as an exciting career and a critical component of the research ecosystem](#), 2030.
 - LECTURE 1 (4 Oct) 'Becoming an RSE' - Jeremy Cohen (Imperial College London).
 - LECTURE 2 (11 Oct) 'Research Software Engineering groups as a way to provide RSE support to researchers' - Dr Kim Martin (Stellenbosch University).
 - LECTURE 3 (18 Oct) 'The value of RSEs for reproducible and applied research' - Dr Martin O'Reilly (Alan Turing Institute).
7. LECTURE 4 (25 Oct) 'How and why research institutes should support RSEs' - Michelle Barker (ReSA).
8. [Research Software Engineer at the Netherlands eScience Center: Job Description](#), 2023.
9. [Research Software Engineers: Creating a Career Path—and a Career](#) (US-RSE and the IEEE Computer Society, 2023).
10. [RSE Survey 2022](#) by Simon Hettrick et al., 2022.
11. RSE in 2030 by Daniel S. Katz and Simon Hettrick, 2023. See [slides](#), [preprint](#), and [paper](#). Provide predictions, including that at least 50 countries globally will have RSE associations), and at least one university Masters of Research Software Engineering program will exist; and many universities will offer RSE certificates or minors at the undergraduate level.
12. [Senior level RSE career paths \(with an s\)](#) by Daniel S. Katz et al., 2021. Identifies a range of possible career paths.
13. [Software and skills for research computing in the UK](#) by Michelle Barker et al., 2024. Recommendations include to enable detailed analysis of how to professionalise RSE

roles, building on existing initiatives such as the international RSE survey; and facilitate collaboration between government, funders, and employers to create national policies aimed at improving standards of employment.

14. [Ten simple rules for recognizing data and software contributions in hiring, promotion and tenure](#) by Iratxe Puebla et al., 2024. Provides advice on areas such as quantitative and qualitative metrics, and existing tools that provide citation information that can be leveraged.
15. [UK Research Software Survey](#), 2014. Analysis highlights the importance of software in conducting research, e.g., that 92% of academics use research software. The dataset is also available.
16. [Understanding Equity, Diversity and Inclusion Challenges Within the Research Software Community](#) by Neil Chue Hong et al., 2021. Analysis of 2018 international RSE survey provides evidence for a lack of diversity in the RSE community. This paper identifies interventions which could address challenges and highlights areas where the community is becoming more diverse.
17. [What is a Research Software Engineer? A definition by the Netherlands eScience Center](#), 2023.
18. [What do we know about RSEs?](#) 2018. The Software Sustainability Institute analyses results from international surveys in 2016, 2017 and 2018 to learn more about RSEs and their work conditions.
19. [Why science needs more research software engineers](#), by Chris Woolston, 2022.